

ABSCESS OF THE RETROPERITONEAL SPACE IN THE RIGHT ILIAC FOSSA AFTER GANGRENOUS-PERFORATIVE APPENDICITIS

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Abstract. *The authors present a clinical observation of an abscess of the retroperitoneal space in the right iliac fossa after acute gangrenous-perforated appendicitis with an atypical retrocecal-retroperitoneal location of the vermiform appendix, which formed around the remaining stone – fecolith (pigment stone). The intraoperative images, the result of histological examination and the conversation with the patient already in the postoperative period, a detailed analysis of the medical history before the patient's admission to the clinic allowed us to assume that during the appendectomy operation, a stone - a fecolith, probably remained in the retroperitoneal space, which 16 years later became the cause of the formation of an abscess. For a long period - of more than 16 years, the patient did not notice any pain and discomfort, or dysuric phenomena. Despite the rarity of the situation, no diagnostic or treatment errors were made.*

Keywords: *retroperitoneal abscess, acute appendicitis, complication of acute appendicitis, fecal stone.*

Introduction. Retroperitoneal abscess is a limited accumulation of pus, which is located between the posterior leaflet of the peritoneum and the intraperitoneal fascia. Abscesses can be single and reach significant volumes, or multiple. Abscesses can form as a result of trauma, surgery, perforation of a hollow organ, metastasis of infection from adjacent structures [1, 2, 3, 16-20]. Retroperitoneal abscesses and phlegmons do not always manifest with the symptoms that make the diagnosis obvious. Being surrounded by large muscle masses and bone structures, they sometimes occur without pronounced clinical manifestations. Most acute purulent processes in the retroperitoneal tissue do not have clearly defined symptoms, and therefore the initial diagnosis is often erroneous [4, 5, 12-15]. Acute appendicitis is one of the most common abdominal diseases encountered by emergency surgical services [7, 8-11].

In retroperitoneal surgery, the outcome of treatment of patients with large inflammatory processes and inflammatory fluid accumulations largely depends on timely diagnosis and the correct treatment strategy [6].

Despite growing awareness and availability of more advanced imaging techniques and other diagnostic tests, extrapulmonary tuberculosis remains a difficult diagnosis due to its often nonspecific manifestations. However, since there are no pathognomonic imaging signs, the diagnosis is ultimately based on histopathological and microbiological findings. The most common sites of abdominal tuberculosis are the intestines, peritoneum, and lymph nodes. Retroperitoneal abscesses, particularly of the lumbar muscle, may develop primarily or secondarily. We report a rare case of massive retroperitoneal abscess simulating extrapulmonary

tuberculosis. After histopathological examination, tuberculous etiology was rejected. After surgical treatment, a favorable outcome occurred.

We present a clinical observation of a retroperitoneal abscess in the right iliac fossa after acute gangrenous-perforated appendicitis with an atypical retrocecal-retroperitoneal location of the vermiform appendix, which formed a fecolith (pigment stone) around the remaining stone.

The patient T.T.U., 30 years old, came spontaneously with complaints of pain in the right lumbar region, frequent urination, fever up to 38 °C, headache.

History of the disease: considers himself ill over the past month, when he began to notice the appearance of aching pain in the right lumbar region. He does not associate the onset of the disease with anything. The patient visited several clinics, was examined by a urologist, an oncurologist. Then he came to us for examination and surgical treatment. He was examined by a doctor and hospitalized in the clinic with a diagnosis of "retroperitoneal abscess".

Medical history: the patient grew and developed in accordance with his age, did not suffer from chronic diseases. The patient underwent appendectomy 16 years ago for acute gangrenous perforated appendicitis with an atypical retrocecal-retroperitoneal location of the appendix. The surgical wound healed by secondary intention. After that, the patient did not report any particular concerns.

Objectively: general condition of moderate severity. Conscious. Adequate. Oriented in space and time. Average nutrition. Body temperature 38.6 ° C. Skin of normal color. Blood pressure 120/80 mm Hg. Pulse is 96 beats/min, satisfactory properties. The rib cage is of regular shape, symmetrical. Both halves of the rib cage participate equally and evenly in the act of breathing. Clear pulmonary sound is determined throughout the entire length of the pulmonary fields on both sides during percussion, vesicular breathing is heard throughout the entire length of the pulmonary fields on the right and left during auscultation. There are no wheezing. Heart activity is rhythmic, tones are sonorous. The tongue is moist, coated with a white coating throughout. The abdomen is not distended, of regular shape, symmetrical, participates in the act of breathing in full. In the right iliac region there is a rough postoperative scar measuring 10x1 cm, without signs of inflammation and hernia formation. On palpation, the abdomen is soft throughout, slightly painful in the right lumbar and mesogastric region, in other areas it is soft and painless, there is no muscle tension or symptoms of peritoneal irritation. The liver and spleen are not palpated, no dullness in the sloping areas of the abdominal cavity is detected. Auscultation reveals active intestinal peristalsis, clearly defined during auscultation. Percussion of the lumbar region on the right is painful, painless on the left. Deep palpation of the lower pole of the right kidney reveals a dense, moderately painful formation. Urination is free, frequent, painless. Stool is regular, of normal color and consistency, no pathological impurities.

Locally: percussion of the lumbar region on the right is painful. Deep palpation of the lower pole of the right kidney reveals a dense, moderately painful formation, the skin over the formation is unchanged, the local temperature is elevated. There is no gas crepitation in the subcutaneous tissue.

Complete blood count: hemoglobin - 113 g / l, leukocytosis $9.34 \times 10^9 / l$ with a band shift of up to 9%. Complete urine analysis: specific gravity - 1010, protein +, epithelium - 2-3/1, leukocytes - 4-5/1, erythrocytes - 3-4/1.

Ultrasound examination: in the projection of the right iliac region, retroperitoneally, an encapsulated fluid formation of an irregular oval shape is visualized, measuring 134x69x94 mm,

has uneven contours with the presence of pockets. Fluid with flocculent suspension and hyperechoic structures of irregular shape are visualized in the cavity, as well as a hyperechoic structure of round shape, 22x20 mm in size, with a clear shadow (corpus?).

MSCT study: in the retroperitoneal space on the right, at the level of VL 4-5, a cystic formation of oval shape is determined with relatively clear uneven contours, 45x46x49 mm in size, density +23 units H. with the presence of a calcification area up to 10 mm in diameter, density +59 units H. This formation is closely adjacent to the lumbosacral muscle on the right. The lumbosacral muscle on the right in this area is thickened, somewhat infiltrated. The kidneys and adrenal glands are of normal shape and location. The renal pelvis and ureters are not dilated. No bone-destructive changes were detected. Lymph nodes in the abdominal cavity are not visualized. There is no free fluid in the abdominal cavity (**Fig. 1**). Excretory MSCT urography shows a picture of moderate right-sided ureterohydronephrosis. No signs of decreased renal excretory function were detected.

Fig. 1. MSCT images in different sections.

Methodology. On ultrasound examination in the projection of the right iliac region, a retroperitoneal encapsulated fluid formation of irregular oval shape is visualized, approximately 134x69x94 mm in size, has uneven contours with the presence of contours. In the cavity, there is fluid with flocculent suspension and hyperechoic structures of irregular shape, also a hyperechoic structure in the lower edge of a round shape, 22x20 mm in size, with a clear acoustic shadow (corpus?). The kidneys are without pathological changes. No free fluid was detected in the abdominal cavity (**Fig. 2**).

X-ray examination of the chest and abdominal cavity: lungs and heart are normal. No free gas or Kloiiber cups were found in the abdominal cavity.

ECG: sinus rhythm, heart rate 96 per minute. The electrical axis of the heart is vertical.

Based on complaints, anamnesis, objective examination data and local status, and the results of instrumental studies, a diagnosis was made: retroperitoneal abscess.

Fig. 2. Ultrasound image: an encysted fluid formation is visualized, also a hyperechoic structure with an acoustic shadow.

Rationale for treatment tactics: given the presence of clinical signs of a retroperitoneal abscess adjacent to the iliac muscle on the right, and the absence of clinical signs of peritonitis, it is assumed that the abscess will be opened through the right iliac region. It was decided to begin the surgical intervention with an incision in the right iliac region with excision of the old postoperative scar and to conduct a revision. Further tactics will be determined depending on the results of the intraoperative revision.

Operation protocol: under general anesthesia in the right iliac region with excision of the old subcutaneous scar, an incision of the skin and subcutaneous tissue up to 12 cm long was made. With some technical difficulties, the retroperitoneal space was reached intermuscularly. The peritoneal sac is tightly fused with the surrounding tissues, which are bluntly separated from the surrounding tissues. When separating the peritoneum from the iliac fossa, white pus, up to 100.0 ml, was released retroperitoneally. Material was taken for bacterial culture. The pus was aspirated. During revision, a dense, round, brown object was found in the abscess cavity, adjacent to the iliopsoas muscle on the right, measuring 1 x 1.2 cm (fecal stone?). **(Fig. 3).**

The fibrin films were removed, after which it was possible to establish the following: a cavity was formed between the iliac-lumbar muscle on the right and the parietal peritoneum of the right iliac fossa. The abscess cavity was treated with a solution of hydrogen peroxide and betadine, sanitized. Reliable hemostasis was achieved. Two drainage tubes were installed in the retroperitoneal space, which were brought out through the contours of the aperture and fixed to the skin. Sanitation of the surgical wound with antiseptic solutions. The wound canal was tightly sutured with guiding sutures. The wound was loosely tamponed with a gauze napkin with an antiseptic solution.

The postoperative period was uneventful. The patient was in the intensive care unit for 24 hours. Body temperature was within subfebrile levels. Complex conservative treatment was administered. Antibacterial therapy was administered taking into account the results of exudate culture for microflora sensitivity (*Escherichia coli* sensitive to ciprofloxacin and amikacin was isolated). On the 2nd day, the patient was transferred from the intensive care unit to the surgery department, activated, and intestinal peristalsis was fully restored. There was independent bowel movement. Local wound treatment consisted of daily dressings and rinsing the abscess cavity and

wound with antiseptic solutions (dioxidine). Hyperemia of the skin around the wound had completely resolved by the 7th day. The drainage tube was removed on the 10th day. On the 7th day after the operation, the patient was discharged from the hospital in a satisfactory condition. The stitches from the postoperative wound were removed 14 days after the operation. The wound healed by primary intention. No signs of suppuration were noted.

Fig. 3. Intraoperative images: removed structure (ficolite), up to 1 cm in size.

Results and discussions. Result of microscopic examination of the material: the material is hard, brown, consists of bilirubin salts.

In our case, at the stage of the patient's admission to the hospital, establishing the correct diagnosis caused significant difficulties and doubts in terms of the etiological development of the abscess. That is why the patient had been to several clinics and even to an oncologist before us. The case clearly demonstrates the "many faces" and "insidiousness" of acute appendicitis. The "chameleon of the abdominal cavity" has many variants of the clinical course and postoperative complications. The participation and analysis of related specialists in establishing the diagnosis in this case made it possible to avoid diagnostic errors. All the attention of the surgical team was initially suspected of a tuberculous abscess.

The patient was from an endemic region. Nephrotuberculosis was also suspected in connection with ureterohydronephrosis on the right. Some of us thought about a possible "textiloma - corpus" and no one thought about a fecal stone. However, the intraoperative picture, the result of the histological examination and the conversation with the patient already in the postoperative period, a detailed analysis of the history of the disease before the patient's admission to the clinic allowed us to assume that during the appendectomy operation for acute gangrenous perforated appendicitis with an atypical retrocecal-retroperitoneal location of the vermiform appendix, a stone - fecolitis - probably remained in the retroperitoneal space, which 16 years later caused the formation of an abscess. This version, in the opinion of the operating surgeons, is closer to the truth.

It is noteworthy that for 16 years the patient did not report any pain and discomfort, or dysuric phenomena. In this case, there is no explanation for why he had no complaints for so long. As a result, despite the rarity of the situation, a diagnostic and therapeutic-tactical error was not made.

Conclusion. To sum up, the development of a retroperitoneal abscess in the late period after acute destructive appendicitis with an atypical localization of the appendix is a possible and rare clinical situation. Atypical localization of pain, the absence of classic signs of an abscess makes the correct diagnosis during the initial examination of the patient extremely difficult. There

are no trifles in surgery, and, unfortunately, diagnostic and tactical errors in the treatment of patients are often made. We hope that the presented material will help surgeons reduce their number and get out of such problematic and difficult situations with dignity.

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